

From individual to joint species distribution models: a comparison of model complexity and predictive performance

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Geographic Distribution of Quality of Fit by Taxon in the Individual Models

The following plots show the geographic distributions of the calibrated probabilities of occurrence (based on maximum likelihood estimates of the taxon-specific parameters) and observations for all taxa in the individual species distribution models. Regions with large blue points or small red points indicate a good quality of fit. Taxa are ordered by decreasing number of occurrences.

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chironomidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 1

D2 = 0.03

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Limoniidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 2

D2 = 0.13

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Simuliidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 3

D2 = 0.09

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Oligochaeta

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 4

D2 = 0.06

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_alpinus

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 5

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Empididae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 6

D2 = 0.02

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_rhodani

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 7

D2 = 0.48

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ceratopogonidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 8

D2 = 0.16

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Psychodidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 9

D2 = 0.04

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Elmidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 10

D2 = 0.39

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Isoperla

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 11

D2 = 0.14

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Planariidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 12

D2 = 0.04

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_muticus

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 13

D2 = 0.28

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gammaridae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 14

D2 = 0.6

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Athericidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 15

D2 = 0.14

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Prostigmata

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 16

D2 = 0.13

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_tristis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 17

D2 = 0.22

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydraenidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 18

D2 = 0.14

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_lateralis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 19

D2 = 0.48

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_mortoni*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 20

D2 = 0.36

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Nematoda

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 21

D2 = 0.07

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Sericostoma

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 22

D2 = 0.17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Scirtidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 23

D2 = 0.2

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habroleptoides_confusa*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 24

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Blephariceridae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 25

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_helveticus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 26

D2 = 0.28

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Brachyptera_risi*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 27

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Sphaeriidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 28

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dixidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 29

D2 = 0.11

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Amphinemura

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 30

D2 = 0.28

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Odontocerum_albicorne*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 31

D2 = 0.19

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dictyogenus

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 32

D2 = 0.41

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Tinodes

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 33

D2 = 0.27

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Tipulidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 34

D2 = 0.03

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Plectrocnemia

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 35

D2 = 0.17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_minima*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 36

D2 = 0.41

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus discolor*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 37

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_loyolaea*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 38

D2 = 0.48

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Epeorus_alpicola*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 39

D2 = 0.29

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_braueri*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 40

D2 = 0.41

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Epeorus_assimilis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 41

D2 = 0.28

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Stratiomyidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 42

D2 = 0.03

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Philopotamus_ludificatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 43

D2 = 0.18

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habrophlebia_lauta*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 44

D2 = 0.25

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dugesiidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 45

D2 = 0.08

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Centroptilum_luteolum*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 46

D2 = 0.22

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_venosus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 47

D2 = 0.24

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_puthzi*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 48

D2 = 0.29

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chloroperla_susemicheli

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 49

D2 = 0.34

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Paraleptophlebia_submarginata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 50

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_picteti*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 51

D2 = 0.41

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_lutheri*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 52

D2 = 0.39

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dytiscidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 53

D2 = 0.06

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Thaumaleidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 54

D2 = 0.18

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_hirticornis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 55

D2 = 0.37

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_alpestris*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 56

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Capnioneura_nemuroides*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 57

D2 = 0.26

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_brevistyla*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 58

D2 = 0.56

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ephemera_danica

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 59

D2 = 0.26

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_picteti*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 60

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Habroleptoides_auberti

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 61

D2 = 0.2

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Metanoea*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 62

D2 = 0.29

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Siphonoperla_torrentium*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 63

D2 = 0.17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Glossosoma

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 64

D2 = 0.18

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_nigra*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 65

D2 = 0.35

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lymnaeidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 66

D2 = 0.15

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_siltalai*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 67

D2 = 0.45

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Electrogena_ujhelyii*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 68

D2 = 0.42

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Rhabdiopteryx

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 69

D2 = 0.23

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Perloides

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 70

D2 = 0.05

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Erpobdellidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 71

D2 = 0.4

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_intricata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 72

D2 = 0.37

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Perla_grandis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 73

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Wormaldia

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 74

D2 = 0.17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Asellidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 75

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Cryptothrix_nebulicola*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 76

D2 = 0.34

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_nimborum*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 77

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Sialidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 78

D2 = 0.12

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ptychopteridae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 79

D2 = 0.35

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydrophilidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 80

D2 = 0.07

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_alpinus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 81

D2 = 0.29

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Glossiphoniidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 82

D2 = 0.39

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus annulatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 83

D2 = 0.25

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Cordulegastriidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 84

D2 = 0.2

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Siphonoperla_montana*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 85

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ephemerella_mucronata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 86

D2 = 0.28

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Serratella ignita*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 87

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_hybrida*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 88

D2 = 0.35

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_nivata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 89

D2 = 0.22

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Anthomyiidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 90

D2 = 0.03

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Leuctra_major

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 91

D2 = 0.48

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lype

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 92

D2 = 0.25

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydroptilidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 93

D2 = 0.26

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus biguttatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 94

D2 = 0.24

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecdyonurus_torrentis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 95

D2 = 0.36

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_degrangei*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 96

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Perla_marginata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 97

D2 = 0.25

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemurella_pictetii*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 98

D2 = 0.05

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ancylus

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 99

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Tabanidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 100

D2 = 0.05

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Polycentropus

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 101

D2 = 0.24

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Potamophylax_cingulatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 102

D2 = 0.22

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_melanchaetes*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 103

D2 = 0.39

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_semicolorata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 104

D2 = 0.52

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_dorieri*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 105

D2 = 0.24

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hydrobiidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 106

D2 = 0.33

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Goeridae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 107

D2 = 0.04

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gyrinidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 108

D2 = 0.4

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Calopterygidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 109

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dinocras

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 110

D2 = 0.18

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lepidostomatidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 111

D2 = 0.15

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Brachyptera_seticornis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 112

D2 = 0.16

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_gratianopolitana*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 113

D2 = 0.66

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_grischuna*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 114

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecclisopteryx_madida*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 115

D2 = 0.66

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Rhagionidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 116

D2 = 0.06

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Physidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 117

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_praemorsa*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 118

D2 = 0.14

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Melampophylax_mucoreus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 119

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_vernus

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 120

D2 = 0.16

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Niphargidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 121

D2 = 0.17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Chloroperla_tripunctata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 122

D2 = 0.29

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_marginata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 123

D2 = 0.5

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Agapetus

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 124

D2 = 0.19

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Torleya_major

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 125

D2 = 0.37

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus nigrescens*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 126

D2 = 0.4

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_intermedia*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 127

D2 = 0.34

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_flexuosa*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 128

D2 = 0.26

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_muelleri*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 129

D2 = 0.5

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_tenuis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 130

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Electrogena_lateralis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 131

D2 = 0.26

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Capnia

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 132

D2 = 0.09

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Haliplidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 133

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dolichopodidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 134

D2 = 0.15

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Micrasema morosum*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 135

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Psychomyia_pusilla*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 136

D2 = 0.45

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_macrura*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 137

D2 = 0.64

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_instabilis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 138

D2 = 0.29

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Syrphidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 139

D2 = 0.12

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Siphonurus_lacustris*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 140

D2 = 0.38

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_stigmatica*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 141

D2 = 0.1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_praecox*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 142

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Corixidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 143

D2 = 0.18

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Planorbidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 144

D2 = 0.36

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_schmidi*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 145

D2 = 0.55

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_vardarensis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 146

D2 = 0.41

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_bucерatus

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 147

D2 = 0.59

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Scathophagidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 148

D2 = 0.15

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_pubescens*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 149

D2 = 0.52

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Allogamus_auricollis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 150

D2 = 0.21

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_torrentium*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 151

D2 = 0.19

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Mystacides*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 152

D2 = 0.49

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Coenagrionidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 153

D2 = 0.38

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dryopidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 154

D2 = 0.12

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Synagapetus_dubitans*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 155

D2 = 0.3

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_rosinae*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 156

D2 = 0.45

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Catagapetus_nigrans*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 157

D2 = 0.36

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Astacidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 158

D2 = 0.65

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Osmylidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 159

D2 = 0.23

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Piscicolidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 160

D2 = 0.39

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Dendrocoelidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 161

D2 = 0.19

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_melanonyx*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 162

D2 = 0.05

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Glyphotaelius_pellucidus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 163

D2 = 0.43

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Psephenidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 164

D2 = 0.24

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gerridae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 165

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_meyeri*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 166

D2 = 0.58

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Rhithrogena_landai

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 167

D2 = 0.53

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Philopotamus_variegatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 168

D2 = 0.13

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Synagapetus_iridipennis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 169

D2 = 0.25

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Halesus_radiatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 170

D2 = 0.22

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_fasciata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 171

D2 = 0.29

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus monticola*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 172

D2 = 0.53

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Lepidoptera

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 173

D2 = 0.17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Veliidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 174

D2 = 0.6

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus alpinus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 175

D2 = 0.23

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ernodes

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 176

D2 = 0.23

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Platycnemididae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 177

D2 = 0.46

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Cnidaria

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 178

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Athripsodes

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 179

D2 = 0.49

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_rivulorum*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 180

D2 = 0.48

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Anabolia

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 181

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_inermis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 182

D2 = 0.69

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_allobrogica*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 183

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ptilocolepus_granulatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 184

D2 = 0.35

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Cloeon_dipterum

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 185

D2 = 0.93

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_nexus

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 186

D2 = 0.53

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_horaria*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 187

D2 = 0.19

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_dinarica*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 188

D2 = 0.41

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_nimborella*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 189

D2 = 0.26

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Bithyniidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 190

D2 = 0.74

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Valvatidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 191

D2 = 0.46

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Aphelocheiridae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 192

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chaetopteryx_major

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 193

D2 = 0.34

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ecclisopteryx_guttulata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 194

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Baetis_niger

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 195

D2 = 0.57

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_hippopus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 196

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_cambrica*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 197

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Mesoveliidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 198

D2 = 0.06

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Holocentropus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 199

D2 = 0.69

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Besdolus_imhoffi*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 200

D2 = 0.78

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Protonemura_auberti*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 201

D2 = 0.14

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_simulatrix*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 202

D2 = 0.48

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_saxonica*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 203

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_dorsalis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 204

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Diplectrona_atra*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 205

D2 = 0.31

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chaoboridae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 206

D2 = 0.17

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Consorophylax_consors

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 207

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habrophlebia_eldae*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 208

D2 = 0.65

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Limnephilus lunatus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 209

D2 = 0.42

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Notidobia_ciliaris*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 210

D2 = 0.32

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_liebenauae*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 211

D2 = 0.36

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Gomphidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 212

D2 = 0.73

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Baetis_nubecularis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 213

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Oecetis_testacea*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 214

D2 = 0.39

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Caenis_luctuosa*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 215

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Hymenoptera

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 216

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Beraea_pullata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 217

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Micrasema_setiferum*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 218

D2 = 0.63

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Cheumatopsyche_lepida*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 219

D2 = 0.63

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Ceraclea_annulicornis*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 220

D2 = 0.63

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Nemoura_cinerea*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 221

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus mixtus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 222

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Agrypnia

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 223

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Habrophlebia_fusca*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 224

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Hydropsyche_pellucidula*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 225

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Sciomyzidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 226

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ephydriidae

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 227

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Halesus_rubricollis*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 228

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_rauscheri*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 229

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Beraea_maurus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 230

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Curculionidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 231

D2 = 0.71

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Notonectidae

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 232

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_glareosa*

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 233

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_pseudosignifera*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 234

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Potamanthus_luteus

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 235

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Heptagenia_sulphurea*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 236

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Micropterna_nycterobia*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 237

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Ceraclea_dissimilis

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 238

D2 = 0.73

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Chrysomelidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 239

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhithrogena_carpatoalpina*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 240

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Leuctra_armata*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 241

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence

- 0.0
- 0.2
- 0.4
- 0.6
- 0.8
- 1.0

Observation

- Absence
- Presence

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Culicidae

iSDM: y ~ Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2 – page 242

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Drusus_chrysotus*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 243

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of *Rhyacophila_rectispina*

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 244

D2 = 1

Probability of occurrence vs observations of Acroloxidae

iSDM: $y \sim \text{Temp FV F100m LUD IAR Temp2}$ – page 245

D2 = 1

